

SECTION OF BIOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL SCIENCES

LONG-TERM RESULTS OF REMOVABLE PROSTHETICS SUPPORTED BY IMPLANTS

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Abstract

Restoring chewing function with various types of prostheses in cases of partial tooth loss remains an important task in orthopedic dentistry. The presence of defects in the dental arch leads to disruptions in the integrity of the dental row and the emergence of morphofunctional changes in the dentoalveolar system, initially occurring near the defect and subsequently spreading throughout the entire dental row. This results in vertical movement and tilting of teeth adjacent to the defect, loss of antagonists, overloading of the remaining teeth, occlusion disturbances, and changes in the temporomandibular joint. The altered functional conditions of the teeth cause metabolic restructuring, which depends on the strength of the chewing load.

Key words: partial edentia, removable dentures, polishing on implants.

In cases of partial edentulism, hemodynamic disorders occur in the tissues surrounding the defect in the dental row, leading to reduced blood circulation and vascular vasoconstriction. New opportunities have emerged with the introduction of artificial supports for dental prostheses into clinical practice, expanding the conditions for removable dental prosthetics. Modern dental implantology, combined with prosthetic treatment, has established itself as an effective method for restoring dental row defects.

Removable prostheses supported by implants, unlike other types of orthopedic treatment, provide a more complete restoration of the chewing function of the dentoalveolar system and ensure rapid adaptation. However, despite advances in implantology, reducing the number of complications and increasing the longevity of prosthetic structures using endosseous implants remains a pressing issue. A review of the literature on the role of functional load in prosthetics with endosseous implants suggests that, despite a large number of clinical and experimental studies, the physiological aspect of the dentoalveolar system's condition remains insufficiently developed.

To address the issue of preventing complications in implantology through orthopedic methods, a comprehensive study of various factors related to metabolic processes in the tissues around the dental row defect is required. Therefore, analyzing dosed loads and objectively assessing the functional state of supporting tissues before and after treatment forms the basis for developing therapeutic and preventive measures to prevent pathological changes in the tissues surrounding natural teeth and endosseous implants.

Most patients needing restoration of the integrity of their dental rows have developed a negative perception of removable prosthetic options due to issues such

as insufficient restoration of chewing function, aesthetics, and unreliable prosthesis fixation. The majority of patients with partial tooth loss (86.1%) prefer fixed prostheses, which are more functional, durable, and aesthetically pleasing. It is known that the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment using bridge prostheses is significantly higher than that of removable constructions.

If prosthetics are not performed in a timely manner for patients with partial tooth loss, it leads to a breakdown of the body's adaptive capabilities, resulting in pathological processes in all components of the dentoalveolar system. These issues prevent proper adaptation to dental prostheses and disrupt the harmony of interactions between all elements of the system.

Various methods of fixation for removable prostheses exist for treating patients with partial tooth loss. In recent years, there has been a significant increase in interest in prostheses that do not use clasps in their design. These methods include bar fixation, magnetic elements, telescopic systems, and, finally, attachment-based fixation systems. The technique of using attachment-retained prostheses is not a simple replication of removable plate or framework prosthetics. Special planning and fabrication algorithms exist for attachment-retained prostheses, and a lack of knowledge in this area can lead to serious mistakes, thereby discrediting the method as a whole.

An important factor in choosing a method for securing a removable prosthesis is the possibility of restoration and repair in cases of loss of one or several supporting teeth, as well as the ability to replace or activate retentive elements. Known methods of securing removable prostheses are not equivalent in terms of these criteria. Removable prostheses with attachment systems provide good splinting of supporting teeth and redistribute chewing loads across all supporting tissues of the prosthetic bed. Excellent fixation, stabilization, and

high functional efficiency have increased interest in these designs in recent years.

The advent of modern, strong, biocompatible alloys for the prosthetic bed, along with high-precision casting and milling methods, has expanded the technological possibilities of manufacturing such prostheses. However, the insufficiently theoretical foundation for using removable prostheses with attachment-based fixation, often based on empirical data, frequently leads to unsatisfactory prosthetic results. A thorough theoretical justification for selecting an orthopedic structure that optimally distributes the load among the available supporting elements is essential. This approach allows for the prediction of successful system functioning and the avoidance of complications.

Publications exist that discuss attachment and telescopic fixation of removable prostheses, but they mainly focus on technological aspects or report certain negative clinical manifestations without addressing the mechanisms behind them. An analysis of domestic and foreign literature shows that, despite significant progress, the issue of orthopedic treatment of patients with dental row defects using removable prostheses with attachment-based fixation remains insufficiently studied and requires further examination.

Study Objective

A clinical and biomechanical assessment of the effectiveness of removable prosthetics in dental prosthetics using implants.

Materials and Methods

A comprehensive examination and treatment of 186 patients with limited dental row defects were conducted using endosseous implants with attachment-based fixation. The group included 10 men (26.3%) and 28 women (73.7%), aged 21 to 60 years, without comorbidities.

During the prosthetic stage, the study group patients received 368 implants, including 335 screw implants (91.0%), 29 short porous implants (7.9%), and 4 flat implants (1.1%). The average number of implants per patient in the study group was 5.0. These implants were subsequently monitored for clinical effectiveness in various prosthetic approaches for patients with complete edentulism (CE).

Among the 73 patients in the study group, 12 (16.4%) underwent implantological treatment using bridge and removable prostheses on both completely edentulous jaws, resulting in a total of 85 completely edentulous jaws being treated (34 upper jaws and 51 lower jaws).

For 57 patients in the first and second control groups, 174 implants were deemed viable and were used for prosthetics with single artificial crowns. At the time of admission for the orthopedic treatment phase, the mean objective implant stability value was -3.2 ± 2.4 in the study group and -3.4 ± 2.4 in the control group.

Results

An analysis of patient outcomes one year after prosthetic completion showed that none of the 368 implants used in prosthetics in the study group were rejected. In contrast, the control group experienced the rejection of one implant that served as a support for a single crown. The implant survival index and clinical

effectiveness of prosthetics in the study group were 100%, compared to 98.9% in the control group.

One year after prosthetic completion, no cases of severe gingival inflammation were observed in either group. However, mild inflammation symptoms, such as slight hyperemia and bleeding upon probing, were noted around 35 implants (9.5%) in the study group and around 7 out of 87 remaining implants (8.1%) in the control group. This difference was not statistically significant.

Gingival recession of 1 mm or less was observed in 16 (4.3%) implants in the study group and 6 (6.9%) implants in the control group. Consequently, gingival recession was significantly less frequent in the study group than in the control group. There were no cases of gingival recession exceeding 1 mm.

Bone tissue assessments revealed that at the time of prosthesis fixation, two implants had areas of resorption in the apical and middle thirds of the endosseous portion, ranging from 2 to 5 mm in diameter with irregular and indistinct contours. However, one year after prosthetic completion, these resorption areas had disappeared, showing a typical bone structure of normal density.

One year after prosthesis fixation, marginal bone loss was identical in both the study and control groups, averaging 0.3 ± 0.2 mm.

Patient satisfaction and quality of life assessments one year post-prosthetics showed that satisfaction levels were 4.2 ± 0.4 in the study group, 4.5 ± 0.5 in the implant control group, and 2.3 ± 0.6 in the conventional removable prosthesis control group.

Thus, patient-reported quality of life scores one year post-prosthesis fixation were:

- Study group: 62.7 ± 5.2 points
- Implant control group: 65.7 ± 3.7 points
- Conventional removable prosthesis control group: 47.8 ± 6.6 points

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